

HISTORICAL AND ARCHEOLOGICAL SCIENCES

EPIGRAPHY AS A HISTORICAL SOURCE (BY THE EXAMPLE OF THE GALLIC EMPIRE)

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Abstract

One of the most important types of archaeological sources is epigraphy, which has become a separate auxiliary historical discipline. Inscriptions are quite objective and, most importantly, contemporary informational material, so the use of epigraphic data in any study can be justified both by the need to confirm the historicity of an event or a specific person, and by extracting the necessary information from the text of the inscription itself. For young researchers, working with such material can be difficult. Therefore, the purpose of this article is to try to clarify the directions and possibilities of using epigraphy in one's research using a specific historical example. This is the reason for the relevance of the work aimed at stimulating interest in working with epigraphic material.

Keywords: historical source, epigraphy, inscriptions, Gallic Empire, Roman Empire, province, altar, mile-post, Germans.

Among the historical sources at the disposal of the historian, epigraphy is one of the most important types, which can be analysed for research as an independent evidence base, or used in combination with other types and types of sources. Such evidence is especially important for complex periods of history, such as the third century A.D., since the written sources are scattered or date back to later centuries.

The localization of inscriptions can be evidence of the region's belonging or subordination to the Roman state, or, conversely, withdrawal from the jurisdiction of the state. The inscriptions can be used to trace the change of power, policy directions, military conflicts, as well as to clarify the names and titles of emperors, and individual events mentioned only in one written source or in passing. For example, the Latin The panegyrics and Ausonius provide valuable information about the revolt in the main city of the Aedui tribe, Augustodunum, which began at the end of the reign of the Gallic emperor Victorinus and whose events can only be clarified through the integrated use of archaeological and epigraphic data.

In general, the inscriptions of the provinces of Britain, Spain, Gaul, and the two Germanys provide valuable information about the socio-economic and political life of the regions. Sometimes they throw light on important events that we could only guess or know from the very brief reports of ancient authors. For example, the fact that Spain recognized Postumus as emperor, and later returned to the jurisdiction of Rome. Thanks to epigraphic data, it is possible to find out the social and ethnic composition of the population of the area, the peculiarities of everyday life, to understand the relationship between various collegiums and organizations existing in these provinces, to learn the nature of crafts, and the dynamics of urban growth.

Sometimes inscriptions concerning the "Gallic Empire" can be found where they are not expected. For example, among the inscriptions of the Danubian regions there are military inscriptions, which provide the

fact that one of the military units, having sworn allegiance to the first Gallic emperor, received his name - I Aelia Dacorum Postumiana, but changed it during the reign of the last Gallic emperor - I Aelia Dacorum Tetricianorum (CIL, VII, 820, 822; Dobo, 719-720).

Of the various categories of inscriptions—municipal, sacral, veteran, military, dedicatory, slave and freedman—it is very difficult to single out those that are of primary importance for this study. They must be evaluated since each of the categories provides the necessary information about the socio-economic development of the "Gallic Empire". The inscriptions give a fairly complete list of handicraft specialties in various regions, show the ethnic and social affiliation of people engaged in certain craft specializations, in mines and mines, and also show which segment of the population is of great importance in a given city or locality. Epigraphy provides data on the functioning of the administration, in particular on conflict situations between Victorinus and the envoy of the Roman emperor, who sought to return the fallen regions to the jurisdiction of the Roman Empire. The existence of colleges of various crafts, merchants, etc., on the territory of Gaul is also noted by epigraphic sources. The inscriptions on the mile stones, as well as the number of these stones, allow us to make assumptions about the relation, for example, of Victorinus or Tetricus, to a certain area of the "Gallic Empire", highlighting the most significant ones. No less important for this study is the policy of the Roman emperors in relation to the "Gallic Empire". Thus, epigraphic data make it possible to determine Aurelianus's claim to regain all the lost provinces, making the Roman state whole and powerful. This can already be traced in the titular of the Roman emperor, which is found in inscriptions made, apparently, immediately after the accession of Aurelianus to the throne.

Marcus Cassianus Latinus Postumus was one of the most influential governors appointed by the Roman Emperor Valerianus. He controlled Gaul and the two

Germans, which is much larger than the other provinces. Postumus had authority and a considerable military force at his disposal. Apparently, Postumus' actions as governor were decisive and effective enough to win the confidence of the population of the provinces, who entrusted him with their security for many years.

Postumus managed to create a state that lasted fifteen years, ten of which he ruled himself. And this time is marked as a time of stabilization and prosperity for the subject provinces not only in written sources, but also confirmed by archaeological data.

Epigraphic sources provide us with unique material. The fact is that ancient historiographers mention only the cognomen of the Gallic emperors. At the same time, epigraphy and numismatics allow us to "get to know" them much better, mentioning not only their full names — Marcus Cassian Latinus Postumus, Marcus Piavonius Victorinus, Gaius Pius Aesuvius Tetricus — but also the titles of the Gallic emperors (CIL, XIII, 9092: I[mp(eratori) Ca]es[ari] | Mar[co Cas]sian[io] | Latin[io Post]umo [p(io)] | f(helixes) inv[icto Au]g(usto), p(ontifici) m(aximo), | trib(unicia) [pot(summer), c]o(n)s(uli) II, | p(atri) p(atriciae), p[roco(n)s(uli). C]ol(onia) N(emetum). CIL, XIII, 12090: [I]mp(eratori) C(aesari) M(arco) Pia[vonio] | Victorino p[ro] fel(ici) inv[icto] | Aug(usto), p(ontifici) m(aximo), trib(unicia) p(otestate), co(n)s(uli), [pro] – | co(n)s(uli). Aug(usta) Tr(everorum), l(eugae) | X[X?]. CIL, XIII, 8964: [I]mp(eratori) Caes(ari) | C(aio) Pio [E]suvio | Tetr[ico] p(io) f(elicis) | inv[icto] | Aug(usto), | p(ontifici) m(aximo), [tr]ib(unicia) p(otestate), p(atri) p(atriciae), | co(n)s(uli), proco(n)s(uli). | C(ivitas) [R(edonum)), while the full name of the rebel Laelianus and Marius, who briefly occupied the throne of the "Gallic Empire", is known from numismatic sources.

The latest finds of epigraphic material have made it possible to make a real discovery. An inscription from the victory altar from Augsburg (In h(onorem) d(omus) d(ivinae) | deae sanctae Victoriae | ob barbaros gentis Semnonum sive Iouthungorum die | VIII et VII kal(endarum) Maiar(um) caesos | fugatosque a militibus prov(inciae) | Raetiae sed et germanicianis | itemque popularibus excussis | multis milibus Itatorum captivor(um) | compos votorum suorum | [[M(arcus) Simplicinius Genialis v(ir) p(erfectissimus) a(gens) v(ices) p(raesidis) | cum eodem exercitu]] | libens merito posuit | dedicata III idus Septemb(res) imp(erator) d(omino) n(ostro) | [[Postumo Au]g(usto) et [[Honoratiano co(n)s(ulibus)]]). [2; 17]. gave unique information about a previously unknown battle in the territory of Rhaetia. Prior to this discovery, it was not known that Postumus, at the request of the governor of Raetia, had arrived with additional military forces in this province to oppose the Germans. Previously, only Paulus Orosius, and the victory was attributed to the emperor Aurelianus (Oros., VII, 22).

According to an inscription on the victory altar from Augsburg, Postumus was called to the aid of the

governor of the province of Rhaetia, through which the Germans of the tribe of the Semnoni or Juthungi passed on a devastating raid into northern Italy. Gallienus apparently did not respond to the pleas for help. On the other hand, Postumus was considered the right hand of the Roman emperor – and to whom, if not him, to turn for help in a difficult foreign policy situation, when part of the troops from Raetia was most likely withdrawn by Aureolus to suppress Ingenui's rebellion. Taking with him, as the inscription says, the legions stationed in both Germaniae, Postumus hastened to Raetia. If this happened as soon as Postumus returned from his "secret" raid beyond the Rhine, then Zonaras' statement that the commander had managed to collect only a part of the booty already distributed to the legionaries at Silvanus' request (Zonaras, XII, 24) becomes understandable. Postumus hurried to the aid of the governor of Raetia.

Taking advantage of the habit of the Germans to return from raids by the same route as they came, Postumus organized an ambush. Semmoni, burdened by the plundered goods and the captives captured in Italy, did not expect the attack and were completely defeated. It seems that the erection of the victory altar falls just at the time when Postumus was proclaimed emperor. According to the inscription, the governor of Rhaetia recognized the authority of the Gallic emperor. Thus, the support of the legions of Raetia became understandable, especially since they were later led by Aureolus¹, whom they also knew and respected well.

Interestingly, the altar has been influenced by the official policy of the Roman emperors in the literal sense: the name and titular of Postumus have been practically erased from the surface. It is probable that the destruction of such altars and any mention of the reign of the Gallic emperors is a characteristic feature of Roman politics. Other rebellious governors ruled for such a short time that they simply did not have time to leave any mention of themselves, while the "Gallic Empire" existed for a long enough time for that difficult period.

Both Germany and Gaul were assigned to Postumus as governor, and they immediately swore allegiance to the newly proclaimed emperor. Then Britain, Spain and Raetia became part of the "Gallic Empire". It is also known that Postumus controlled the coast of Flanders and Brittany, but in what period of time remains questionable, since the main sources are archaeological data and numismatics. However, this does not refute this assumption, as evidenced by the previously mentioned unexpected find of a well-preserved altar-piece from Augsburg.

The exact date of the accession of Britain and Spain to the Postumus is unknown. The inscriptions of the Roman Emperor Gallienus are not recorded in these territories, but the spread of the inscriptions of Postumus and the heir of his power is characteristic. In addition, mile pillars dating from the reign of the first Gallic emperor have been found in Spain, one of which

¹ Aureolus was the right-hand man of the Roman Emperor Gallienus and led his reformed cavalry, on which Gallienus placed so much hope. It was Aureolus who led one of the punitive campaigns against the "Gallic Empire". In 266 he rebelled and, with the support of loyal troops, was proclaimed

emperor in Mediolanum (present-day Milan), taking control of northern Italy. The following year, Aureolus swore allegiance to the first Gallic emperor, placing at his disposal the cavalry, the mint, and the captured territory.

contains an inscription bearing his name (ILS, 562; CIL, XII, 4943). In Cadiz, a mile stone with the name of Postumus was found, dating back to 260 AD, which allows us to say that Spain made a fairly quick decision about its position. Until the reign of Claudius II Gothicus, Spain was under the rule of the first Gallic emperor, according to archaeological, epigraphic, and numismatic evidence. Evidence of Britain and Spain coming under the control of the Gallic emperor is the fact that two British and one Spanish legions disappear from Gallienus' coins. It is known that the Spanish legion VII Gemina was transferred from the city of Léon to the Gallic city of Lugdunum (modern Lyon), which was under the control of Postumus, in order to ensure the security of the entire region. It should also be noted that one of the mints of the Gallic emperor was located in Lugdunum. Archaeological and numismatic data provide information that the Gallic emperors minted coins at the mints of Lugdunum, Narbonna, Colonia-Agripina, Augusta Treverorum, Mogontiacus, as well as in a number of mint workshops in the subject territories. Archaeological excavations of the last decade provide unique information about the numerous workshops in Britain.

Part of the British Legio I Ulpia Victrix was stationed in Bonn, which was the headquarters not only of the governor of the provinces of Upper and Lower Germany, but also the base of the classis Germanica fleet. The initiator of the revolt, Legio I Minervia, was also originally located here, as evidenced by the coins of Postumus issued later (Elmer 309 (Aur.), 313 (Ant.): MINER(va) FAVTR(ix)). According to epigraphic data, the legion was served by natives of different provinces, for example: 6 legionnaires originating from the Three Gauls, 9 from Germany, 2 from Noricum, 1 from Pannonia, 1 from Dalmatia, 4 from Thrace, 1 from Syria (CIL, XIII, 1832; CIL, XIII, 1846: Cassianus Lupulus (Lyon); IGR, III, 80 = ILS, 9476: Victorius Sabinus, Velocassimus (Heraclea Pontica); CIL, XIII, 1844 = Riese, 608: Aurelius Primus, civis Remus (Lyon); CIL, XIII, 1887: Aludisas (Lyon); Adnamatius Dubitatus (Bonn). CIL. X. 3896: Silvanus Silvester, natus Col. Agrippinense (Caserta); CIL, XIII, 1844 = Riese, 608: Modestinius Peregrinus, civis Agrippiensi (Lyon); CIL, XIII, 8002: Opponius Paternus, Agrippinensis (Lessenich); CIL, XII, 8091 = Riese, 2290/1: T. Manilius Genialis, Agripp., T. Manilius Iucundus ? (Bonn); CIL, XIII, 8278 = Riese, 520: Aurelius Aristaenetus pater, Aurelius Aristides filius, Agripp. (Köln); CIL, XIII, 8566: Cassius Victor (Neub): CIL, XIII, 8040 = Riese, 527: ignotus natione Frisus (Bonn): Iulius Betto (Rom); CIL, XIII, 8068: Haldavvon[ius] V[erus ?] (Bonn)).

The sources at our disposal allow us to conclude that the following military units swore allegiance to Postumus [a German researcher is certain of the oath of only six legions – 17, s. 89; 11, p. 27]: the Legio I Minervia, who may have been transferred to Augusta Treverorum (Cohen, V, 2, 387, 259–462), the Legio XXX Ulpia victrix (Cohen, V, 2, 394, 552–557), who later supported Leliana's rebellion. Both legions were stationed in Lower Germany. The Legio XXII Primigenia was stationed in Mogontiacus (Upper Germany), the Legio

VIII Augusta was based in the Argentoratus (Strasbourg) and with its oath decided the fate of Upper Germany. Part of the legion was stationed at Augusta Treverorum; Legio VI Ulpia Victrix of Britain, part of which was stationed at Bonna in 260 (AE, 1930, Vol. 35) and managed to visit Rhaetia at about the same time (in Britain the legion was based at Glevum: CIL, VI, 3346); The Legio II Gallica, stationed at Arausionus (Orange), the Legio VIII Ulpia Victrix of Spanish, relocated to Lyon due to the invasions of Germanic tribes. The XX Legion Valeria Victrix of Britain (Chester), part of which may have been vexillationes, was redeployed to the Rhine and Danubian frontiers, in particular to Mogontiacus [28, p. 428]. Legion V Macedonia supported the revolt of Ingenuus and Regallianus, and after their defeat joined the "Gallic Empire" (Cohen., VI.2, 375, 61; CIL, V, 1881). In 275, the legion returned to Aurelian's control. However, its location was the Danube, the territory of the Tres Daciae, apparently on the border with Rhaetia (IV Macedonia was based on the Rhine). Also worth mentioning is the Legio IV Flavia, stationed in Moesia Superior; Legio XIII Gemina, stationed in Gallia, Legio II Augusta of Britannia (Richborough) [28, p. 435], XIV Gemina of Pannonia Superior, Legio III Gallica, which may have been transferred to the "Gallic Empire" [28, p. 434]. With a high degree of probability, III of Italy from Raetia (Cohen., V.2, 268–271; ILS, 8882). Legio II Trajana of Egypt, called Germanic (CIL, III, 1205), was relocated to northern Italy (where the revolt of Aureolus, who swore allegiance to Postumus) took place, and X Fretensis, stationed in Palestine, was sent to Britain [28, p. 435]. Both legions seem to have sworn allegiance at the end of Postumus' reign. This explains why the last three legions appear on the coins of Victorinus and are absent from Gallienus.

Doubts are raised by the Legio II Augusta, called in one of the inscriptions of this period "Germanicianarum", "Britannicianarum" (CIL, XIII, 3228), as well as VI Gallicana, stationed on the Rhine. The information about this legion appears only in sources dating back to the reign of Aurelian, who tried to regain control not only of the provinces, but also of the legions (SHA. XXVI, 7, 1). Of the auxilia auxilia, of which there is information: in Britain, the numerus Frisiorum (CIL, VII, 415) and their cohort (CIL, VII, 214), the numerus of the Sarmatians (CIL, VII, 218), the second cohort of the Tungri, which even under Gordian had the honorary title of Latin citizens (CIL, VII, 882), which included as subdivisions the German hundreds, such as the pagus Vellaus and the pagus Condrustis (CIL, VII, 1072, 1073); numerus Hnaudifridi, who wrote an inscription to the goddesses Alaysiagas, to whom two inscriptions cives Tuihanti cunei Frisiorum were dedicated (ILS, 4760, 4761). There is also information about another military unit. One of the inscriptions mentions praefectus equitum alae Sebussianae Postumianae Flavius Ammausius. Earlier inscriptions mention a military unit based in Lancaster, praefectus II Gallorum Sebosiana (CIL, XVI, 48, 69). Thus, from the epigraphic data, we know of the units of the Britannia inferior that swore allegiance to Postumus: equitibus

alae Sebussianae Postumianiae (RIB, 605) from Lancaster; cohorts I Aelia Dacorum Postumiana (RIB, 1883, 1886) of Birdoswald near Hadrian's Wall, and a detachment assigned to the first Gallic emperor from the *res publica civitatis Carvetiorum* (AE, 1965, № 216) from a settlement also near Hadrian's Wall. From Britannia superior - Isca Silurum (RIB, 2255) from Mergem, a military unit from Trecastle Hill (RIB, 2260), a Deva unit from Chester and Segontium from Kervanon (JRS, 1962, 52, № 24), a subdivision of Isca Dumnoniorum (RIB, 2232) of Exeter.

Of the auxiliary units located in other regions, the following are known from epigraphic data: ala Indiana Gallorum, in which, apparently, Victorinus served. It was this part that went over to the side of Postumus in 264-265 [17, s. 70; 1, s. 19; 22, p. 166; 27, s. 832]. In Upper Germany, units from the Colonia Agrippina and Noviomagus (CIL, XIII, 6779, 9092; BRGK, 1938, 27, 120); in Lower Germany, *custos armorum Veranius Verinus* from Bonn (AE, 1930, № 35, 54). From Tarraconian Spain, military units from León, San Miguel de Confino, Puerto de Sevier, and Acci from Cadiz were placed at Postumus's disposal (CIL, II, 4919, 4943, 5736). Curiously, one of the units was provided by the *Scorcia Onnacau Ammiae Caelionicae ex gente Peniorum*. From the testimonies of ancient authors, it is known that the Gauls placed at the disposal of the first Gallic emperor auxiliaries and cavalry (Eutr., IX, 9; SHA. XXIII, 4, 4; 7, 1; XXIV, 3, 4; 6, 2; Zosim., I, 38; Zonaras, XII, 24).

The inscriptions of the provinces that became part of the "Gallic Empire"—Britannia, Hispania, three Galliae and the two Germaniae, and Rhaetia—provide valuable information about the socioeconomic and political life of the regions. They cover important events that we could only have imagined or known from the very brief accounts of ancient authors. In particular, the inscriptions on the mile pillars, as well as the number on them, allow us to make assumptions about the attitude of the Gallic emperors to a certain area of the "Gallic Empire", highlighting the most significant ones². For example, a mile post with the inscription and name Victorinus found in the area of the Decumate Fields allows us to say that this territory was under the control of the Gallic emperors for some time [17, p. 269]. On the other hand, coins of Postumus and one of his successors, Marius, have been found in the area [9, p. 235; 24, p. 162-164]. All this suggests that the Decumate Fields were under the control of the "Gallic Empire", since only in this case could this region serve as a buffer zone.

According to epigraphic data, Gaul in the 3rd century A.D. was a diverse territory in terms of class and ethnic composition (CIL, XII, 2522, 3349; XIII, 1943, 1974, 2020, 4335) [14, p. 259; 4, p. 5-7; 25, p. 27]. The local population continued to be divided into pagi (CIL,

XII, 1114, 1376, 2556, 2611; XIII, 2949, 3106, 5063, 5064, 6211). Epigraphic evidence proves that pagi persisted in both Spain and Britain during this period [3, p. 274-275; 13, p. 63; 26, p. 164, 200].

The inscriptions give a fairly complete list of handicraft specialties in various regions, show the ethnic and social affiliation of people engaged in certain craft specializations, in mines and mines, and also show which segment of the population is of great importance in a given city or locality. The inscriptions provide us with the names of the professions prevalent in this period, such as lapidaries of precious stones, processors of precious metals, goldsmiths, goldsmiths and silversmiths (CIL, XIII, 2024, 2828, 2901, 4391, 4465, 4475, 5154; XII, 446, 4391, 4456, 4474, 4475). According to epigraphic data, slaves and convicts worked in the mines, as well as small landowners whose farms were located in the vicinity of the mines (*Pagani ferrarienses* — CIL. XIII. 384, 1150; XII. 3336) [Grenier A. VOL. II. P. 957]. Some mines were privately owned and located within estates, while others were owned by individual towns and civitates (D. M. *Primionis ferrariae (um servi) vitalis contules* — CIL. XII. 3336) [19, p. 11-12; 20, p. 97]. The extraction and processing of iron gave rise to a number of craft specializations and professions: blacksmiths, stampers; gunsmiths and related manufacturers of armor, helmets, etc. (CIL, XIII, 2828, 384, 5699, 1-12; 5701, 1-68; 10029. 1-27; XII, 3355, 4475; ILTG, 355). It should be noted that metal works (including bronze and precious metals) were quite diverse.

Archaeological data allow us to note the intensification of construction on the territory of the "Gallic Empire". The inscriptions not only confirm this fact, but also provide irrefutable proof that the construction was carried out not only at the expense of the municipalities [5, p. 167-168], but also at the expense of rich and influential people, who began to willingly invest money in their construction [12, p. 241-242.]. It is also noteworthy that the supply of building materials and human resources was often carried out by private individuals or private partnership [5, p. 167]. For example, a certain Probia Justina restored the temple of the local goddess in Hove (Britain) entirely at her own expense for her son Tercinius Justina (CIL, XIII, 7917). On another occasion, at Remagenus, the prefect restored a clock (*horologium*) at his own expense (CIL, XIII, 7800).

The resumption of work in the mines for the extraction of precious metals, in craft workshops, in stone quarries, and the intensification of civil construction are just some of the factors in the economic success of the policy of the Gallic emperor, who, despite difficult times, managed to restore the old trade relations of the regions and establish new ones, going beyond the borders of the "Gallic Empire".

²The Decumate section of the limes, located in the fields of the same name, was about 382 km long, with a small concentration of auxiliary units, remote (even too) legion camps, and the absence of a natural defensive line in the form of a large water barrier, represented a weak link in the defence of Rome on the Rhine. The Decumate fields were annexed under the Roman emperor Domitian, at the same time a section of the

limes was built from the river Lahn to the confluence of the Kindig with the Main. Under Trajan, it was built the section between the Main and the Neckar. Reconstruction of the limes began during the reign of Hadrian. Under Antoninus Pius, the Odenwald section of the limes was advanced eastward around 30 km.

Respect, recognition and trust in Postumus was so great that after his death, the heirs failed to preserve the integrity of the created state. One by one, the regions gradually came under the rule of the Roman emperors, apparently seeing in the stabilization of the central authority greater benefits for development and security.

Sources are rather vague about the origin of the Gallic emperor Victorinus, who was, in fact, the heir of Postumus (SHA. XXIV, 4; Eutr., IX, 9, 3; Oros., VII, 22; Aur. Vict., De Caes., XXXIII, 12; Epitom., XXXIV, 3; Pol. Silv., 49). However, the wealthy house excavated in Augusta Treverorum (present-day Trier) yielded much more information than all the narrative sources. A mosaic with an inscription was found inside the house (M(arcus) Pia(v)onius Victo|rinus tribunus p|r(a)et[oria]norum | [d(e) ? s(u) ? oder domum ? restituit]. Trier. CIL, XIII, 3679 = ILS. 563), which makes it possible to assert that it belonged to the Gallic emperor Victorinus, who apparently came from among the wealthy Gallic aristocracy [23, p. 44–46. Taf. 42, 2 (Mosaik), 48, 5 (Inscription); 10, s. 19], which previously could only be inferred based on the special position and influence of his mother Victoria. There is one inscription that allows us to assert that Victoria is a historical person (Dis Manibus. | L(ucii) Victorini Victoria | piissima Victorini | uxor [. .]rin[. .]vato | e- -v- -frumen(to)? This only surviving inscription seems to prove the reality of the existence of Victoria, Victorinus' mother. Landres. CIL, XIII, 5868). Moreover, ancient authors treated it with special respect and admiration (SHA. XXIV, 6, 2; XXXI, 4; XXV, 25, 4), because it was she who contributed to the proclamation of subsequent Gallic emperors, including the Roman senator Tetricus.

During his reign, Victorinus lost the eastern part of Narbonne Gaul (Britannia – RIB, 2246; Hispania – CIL, II, 3834, 4879, 4505; Narbonnaise – CIL, XII, 2228, 5511). Modern scholars suggest that this territory took either a vacillating position [29, p. 464] or relative neutrality, since it was in this region that refugees from the rebellious Augustodunum were hiding [13, p. 41; 20, s. 159]. In any case, from the very beginning of the reign of Claudius of Gotha, part of Narbonne Gaul came under the rule of Rome. An inscription from Grazianople, dated 269, is made in honor of the Roman emperor, showing that this part of the Narbonensis recognized Claudius II, and that Julius Placidianus was stationed here with the cavalry (CIL, XII, 2228). Thus, it became known about the conflict between Victorinus, who sought to preserve the integrity of the "Gallic Empire", and a representative of the administration of the Roman emperor, sent to this region with the opposite goal. The presence of Placidianus in the eastern part of Narbonne Gaul is also known from another inscription (CIL, XII, 1551.). Nevertheless, the city of Vienne remained part of the "Gallic Empire" for the entire period of its existence [16, IV, p. 332; 21, p. 143–158], while the constant rivalry of that city with Lugdunum must have driven it into the opposite camp. Victorin's inscriptions have been found in various areas, for example, in Mainz, Nantes, Lescorlaud, Sainte-Meloire-des-Bois (CIL, XIII, 9009; XIII, 8999; XIII, 9006; XIII, 9012), in Belgica (Brimont – CIL, XIII, 9040;

Kyllward – CIL, XIII, 12090; Upper Germania – AE, 1971, №279), Britain (at the same time, it should be borne in mind that an inscription by Claudius of Gotha has also been found in Britain: RIB, 2246), and are found on the Nantes-Tours-Bourges-Dijon-Besançon-Basel line (CIL, XIII, 8958; CIL, XIII, 8959, 8961; Bank account details. 2241 = ILS, 565).

The religious preferences of the civilian and military population of the regions that became part of the "Gallic Empire" are also important. It should be noted that the religious policy of the Gallic emperors is most widely represented in coin legends, on the basis of which we can speak of the worship of Hercules (a set of dedicatory inscriptions on altars from Glan and Gaul: AE, 1954, № 101–103), Mercury, Fortuna (dedications to Mercury were especially popular in Mogontiacus: AE, 1951, № 136; 1953, № 42; 1954, № 91, 154; 1955, № 110, 143), Apollo (AE, 1954, № 145; 1950, № 233), Jupiter (in particular, three inscriptions dedicated to Apollo were made by a Gallic merchant trading with Britain: AE, 1953, № 269; AE, 1950, № 27, 140, 231; 1952, № 196), and Mithras (it is known that this oriental deity is especially widespread among the military: AE, 1950, № 199; 1953, № 2). The religious quests of the population, especially of Gaul, were bound to lead to a return to the old gods and the old religion. Moreover, close contacts were again established between the continental and insular Celts. Many inscriptions in Spain, Gaul and Britain are dedicated to tribal gods (AE, 1949, №93 (Mother Goddess), 94, 95, 101; 1950, № 22–24, 28, 213, 219–220, 222–225; 1952. №84, 86 (Mother Goddess), 130; 1953, №99 (dedication to the little-known Germanic deity Usneihae), 260–261; 1954, № 92, 94–96, 107 (Hammer Sylvanus), 130; 1955, № 30, 234) [10, p. 300 e al.]. It is during this period that a return to traditional Celtic beliefs, such as the dedication to Epona, is characteristic. This, as well as much of the above, became the basis for the assertion that it is possible to talk about such a phenomenon as the "Celtic Renaissance". However, in the centuries since the conquest of Gaul, much has changed, both within the region and in the worldview of the Gauls who inhabited it. The influence of neighbouring provinces, Romanization are just some of the factors that refute the hypothesis of the revival of Celtic civilization.

In 274, the "Gallic Empire" came to an end. The regions that were part of it were gradually returned to the jurisdiction of the Roman emperors. The idea of a "Gallic Empire" took deep roots, but the official policy of the Roman emperors and their administration was aimed at the complete destruction of any evidence of separatism in the middle of the third century. Mile posts erected by Gallic rulers were used to build new defensive fortifications, or simply discarded and replaced with similar ones, but with the names of Roman emperors. The deeds of the Gallic emperors were credited to the emperors of Rome, so that after a while historians had almost no information about the "Gallic Empire". An entire period of time was erased from the official chronology, and, as a result, from the entire history. But no matter how hard Roman official propaganda tried to erase any reminder of the times of the Gallic emperors, it failed.

Interest in the problem is growing with the discovery of more and more new facts, which at the end of the 19th century were only hypotheses, and now, thanks to numerous epigraphic findings, have received a solid evidence base, especially in combination with other types and types of sources. Thus, epigraphy as a separate type of sources can be used in research as an independent basis for proving certain processes or phenomena, and in a complex of other types of sources to deepen the understanding of the events that took place, confirm the facts, and provide an additional basis for the evidentiary base of the research.

List of abbreviations:

- AE – L'Année Épigraphique. Paris.
 ANRW – Aufstieg Niedergang der Römischen Welt.
 Aur. Vict. De Caes. – Aurelius Victor Sextus. De Caesaribus. Origo gentis Romanae. Liber de viris illustribus urbis Romae. Epitome de Caesaribus / ed. Fr. Pichlmayr, corr. by R. Gruendel, Leipzig 1966.
 BRGK – Berichte der Römisch-Germanischen Kommission
 CIL – Corpus Inscriptionum Latinarum.
 Cohen – Cohen H. Description historique des monnaies frappées sous l'Empire romain : Tom. I–VI. Paris, 1881–1886.
 Dobo – Dobo A. Inscriptiones extra fines Pannoniae Daciaeque repertae ad res earundem provinciarum pertinentes. Budapest, 1975.
 Elmer – Elmer G. Die Münzprägung der Gallischen Kaiser in Köln, Trier und Mailand. Bonn, 1941.
 Epitom. – Pseudo-Aurelius Victor. Epitome de Caesaribus. URL: <http://thelatinlibrary.com/victor.caes2.html> (дата обращения 27.02.2023).
 Eutr. – Eutropius. Breviarium Ab urbe condita / Ed. C. Santini (Teubner). Leipzig, 1979.
 ILS – Dessau H. Inscriptiones Latinae Selectae. Berlin, 1892–1916.
 JRS – Journal of Roman Studies.
 NC – The Numismatic Chronicle. The Royal Numismatic society. Cambridge Univ. Press. London.
 Oros. – Orosius Paulus. Historiae adversus paganos / Ed. C. Zangemeister. (Teubner). Leipzig, 1889.
 Pol. Silv. – Polemius Silvius. Fragmentae / ed. T. Mommsen // Gesammelte Schriften VII (Philologische Schriften). Berlin, 1909. 633–667.
 RIB – Collingwood R. G., Wright R. P. The Roman Inscriptions of Britain: T. 1–3. Oxford, 1965.
 Riese – Riese A. Das Rheinische Germanien in den antiken Inschriften. Berlin, 1914.
 RE – Revue Épigraphique. Paris.
 SHA – Scriptores Historiae Augustae: Bd 1-2 / ed. E. Hohl. Lipsiae, 1965.
 ZfN – Zeitschrift für numismatik.
 Zonaras – Zonaras. Epitome Historiarum / Ed. Dindorf. Leipzig, 1870.
 Zosim. – Zosimus. Historia Nova / Ed. F. Paschoud. Paris, 1971.

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